

DETERMINANTS OF EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH THE INTERVENING VARIABLE OF JOB SATISFACTION: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN THE WEST CIKARANG INDUSTRIAL AREA, WEST JAVA, INDONESIA

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze and address the research gaps in various previous research results, in addition to the phenomenon where Job Satisfaction functions as an inconsistent intervening variable that can explain Employee Performance. Things like that are the considerations for conducting this research. This type of research is quantitative descriptive with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method in the LISREL application. The research objects used in this study are employees of Manufacturing Companies in the West Cikarang Industrial Area, West Java during 2023 with a population of 428 employees and a total sample of 207 employees. The results of this study can be explained that all exogenous variables in this study can explain their influence significantly and are positively correlated with endogenous variables. These results are expected to assist management in organizing and maximizing the ownership of its human resources.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Integrity, Teamwork, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The current global situation is characterized by complex dynamics and rapid changes across various sectors. The global economy continues to face significant challenges, such as financial instability, trade wars, and inflation. The COVID-19 pandemic, which has gripped the world since late 2019, has exacerbated the economic situation by causing recessions in many countries. Meanwhile, recovery efforts are underway, focusing on mass vaccination and economic stimulation. Technology and digitalization also play a crucial role in these efforts, with many companies shifting to digital business models to survive and thrive.

On the social front, demographic change and urbanization also bring new challenges and opportunities. The global population continues to grow, with an increasing number of elderly people in many countries. This requires adjustments to social and health policies to meet the needs of an aging population.

Furthermore, global migration and the growth of megacities create complex social dynamics, including issues of inequality, access to education, and healthcare. Disparities between social groups are also a major concern, particularly in the context of access to technology and education.

In the political realm, the world is witnessing rising geopolitical tensions and shifting international alliances. Issues such as climate change, energy security, and human rights are at the top of the global agenda. Countries need to work together to address these global challenges, while also addressing pressing domestic issues. Diplomacy and negotiation are more crucial than ever in maintaining international peace and stability. Meanwhile, innovation and multilateral cooperation are needed to effectively address global challenges and create a more sustainable and prosperous future for all.

An independent, advanced, just, and prosperous nation is inextricably linked to the phenomenon of National Development. Globalization has accelerated the flow of information, trade, and human mobility, but has also given rise to increasingly intense competition between nations. On the other hand, changes in demographic structure, particularly the increasing number of productive-age residents, create both opportunities and potential problems if not balanced by improvements in the quality of human resources and adequate job creation.

The Covid-19 pandemic has exposed the vulnerabilities of health, economic, and social systems, serving as a reminder of the importance of national resilience across various sectors. In an increasingly complex and dynamic workplace, organizational effectiveness is highly dependent on key factors influencing employee behavior and satisfaction. One topic attracting attention in management research is the influence of transformational leadership, integrity, and teamwork on job satisfaction and their implications for employee performance.

Moving toward a transformation of leaders who reflect the characteristics of the millennial generation in the face of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 and witnessing increasingly rapid and advanced technological developments, the global community is not only leveraging technological advances but is also transforming knowledge-based competition, shifting from tangible assets to intangible ones. This includes the development of educational and research facilities.

The need for employment is an undeniable demand to obtain compensation to meet the necessities of life. Organizations, agencies, or companies providing employment have special rules in their operations that are usually still in line with regulations issued by the government. Ideally, an organization should be an organization that can provide comfort, facilitate and manage its employees well in carrying out their responsibilities and duties because proper human resource management is a determinant of success in achieving an organization's goals.

One important aspect that organizations need to pay attention to in managing human resources is employee job satisfaction. and technology is also used as a tool to fulfill daily needs and not only the Manufacturing Industry is required to be able to increase its productivity, competence, and work efficiency in order to continuously achieve sustainability which will impact the performance of the company's employees. The development of the Manufacturing Industry has succeeded in reaching the top ten in the world and becoming the largest manufacturing industry base in ASEAN with a contribution of 20.27% to the national economy. Currently, the manufacturing industry is able to shift its role from commodity-based to manufacturing-based.

The government is trying to transform the economy to focus more on the development process of non-oil and gas industries. The manufacturing industry is considered more productive and can have a broad ripple effect, increasing the added value of raw materials, increasing the workforce, generating the largest source of foreign exchange, and contributing significantly to taxes and customs duties. This will undoubtedly drive national economic growth and increase competitiveness domestically, regionally, and globally. Source: Investment Coordinating Board (BKPM).

In Indonesia, the implementation of manufacturing is regulated by the Republic of Indonesia Law No. 3 of 2014 concerning Industry and Government Regulation (PP) No. 28 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of the Industrial Sector. According to the law, the manufacturing industry is defined as an economic activity that includes production activities that transform basic goods mechanically, chemically, or semi-finished and/or goods of less value into goods of higher value. The success of an industry is certainly inseparable from the role of human resources who play a vital role in carrying out various production processes, equipment management, and technology development. The scale of Medium and Large Industries is determined based on the following criteria: number of workers, the amount of accumulated investment value, turnover, specifically in the rice milling industry using machine scales to ensure production runs smoothly, efficiently, and produces high-quality products according to established standards.

The Indonesian Standard Industrial Classification consists of: Food Industry, Beverage Industry, Tobacco Processing Industry, Textile Industry, Apparel Industry, Leather Industry, Leather Goods and Footwear Industry, Wood Industry, Paper Industry, Printing/Reproduction Industry, Coal/Petroleum Products Industry, Chemical/Chemical Products Industry, Pharmaceutical/Traditional Medicine Industry, Rubber/Plastics Industry, Non-Metallic Minerals Industry, Base Metals Industry, Non-Machine Metal Products/Equipment Industry, Computer/Electronic/Optical Products Industry, Electrical Plate Industry, Machinery Industry, Motor Vehicle Industry, Transportation Equipment Industry, Furniture Industry, Management Industry, Service Industry/Machine and Equipment Installation Industry. Thus, the classification is based on the laws applicable in the Republic of Indonesia.

The study of human resource management is an important, widely recognized, and beneficial endeavor. Human resource management is about dealing with coworkers humanely, business administration, and the strategies, procedures, rules, and processes that affect employees within an organization. Human resource management is the process of acquiring, training, assessing, and compensating employees and of managing labor relations, health and safety, and matters related to fairness Husaini and Utama, (2021).

Armstrong's Handbook and Taylor (2020) identify the role of human resource management to (a) support the organization in achieving its goals by developing and establishing strategies that are integrated with the organizational strategy, (b) contribute to the development of a high-performance culture, (c) ensure that the organization has the talented, skilled, and engaged people it needs, (d) encourage the implementation of an ethical approach to human resource management.

Based on publications in various journals that employee performance can be defined in Amerta, et., al. (2021), argues that employee performance is influenced by individual factors (abilities, skills, family background, work experience), psychological factors (perception, role, attitude, motivation, and personality), and organizational factors (organizational structure, job design, leadership, and reward systems).

In Tirtayasa, S & Pasaribu, H. K (2020), performance is the work results in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to them. Furthermore, Kashmir in Dwie Egie (2019) states that performance is the result of work and work behavior achieved in completing tasks and responsibilities given within a certain period.

Similarly, Afandi (2018) states that performance is the work results that can be achieved by an individual or group of people in a company according to their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, not violating the law and not contrary to morals and ethics.

In Litra Diantara, et., al., (2022), Septian Aris Munandar, (2022), the results of the research that has been conducted can be concluded that transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational commitment, transformational leadership has a significant effect on employee performance, transformational leadership has a significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment.

The results of research conducted by Ni Kadek Tya Yudiastuti & I Gusti Salit Ketut Netra, (2021), transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, this shows that the better the transformational leadership style implemented by superiors, the more it will increase employee job satisfaction.

These results are not different from those conducted by Damai Daeli, et.al., (2024), but different from the results in Rima Handayani & Eni Puji Astuti, (2023), also different in Nainggolan, et.,al., (2020), Muhammad Hatta, et.,al., (2021), Muhammad Taufik Lesmana, et.,al., (2020).

HYPOTHESIS

H₁: Transformational leadership influences job satisfaction.

H₂: Integrity influences job satisfaction.

H₃: Teamwork influences job satisfaction.

H₄: There is an influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance.

H₅: There is an influence of Integrity on Employee Performance.

H₆: There is an influence of Teamwork on Employee Performance.

H₇: There is an influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance.

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study using a quantitative approach to hypothesis testing. The research subjects were employees of a manufacturing company in the West Cikarang Industrial Estate, West Java, during 2023.

The population was 428 employees. Furthermore, the researcher used a proportional random sampling technique. The sample members were determined by selecting representatives from each group in the population, the number of which was adjusted to the number of subjects in each group. To determine the minimum sample size required, if the population size is known, the Slovin formula can be used, assuming a tolerable sampling error rate of 5% (Sugiono, 2016):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size, 428

e = sampling error rate, which is 5%.

The results of the sample size calculation are as follows:

$$n = \frac{428}{1 + 428 (0,05)^2}$$

$$n = 206,76 \approx 207$$

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables of Transformational Leadership (KT)

Variables	Dimension	Indicator	Code
Transformational Leadership (KT)	Idealized Influence	Pride / Role Model	KT1.1
		Trust	KT1.2
		Loyalty	KT1.3
		Respect	KT1.4
	Inspirational Motivation	Motivating subordinates	KT2.5
		Achieving goals	KT2.6
		Ability	KT2.7
	Intellectual Stimulation	Creative thinking	KT3.8
		Generating new ideas	KT3.9
		Problem solving	KT3.10
	Individualized Consideration	Care	KT4.11
		Appreciation	KT4.12
		Advising through interaction	KT4.13

Table 2: Operational Variables Integrity (IT)

Variables	Dimension	Indicator	Code
Integrity (IT)	Honesty	Empathy	IT1.1
		Not easily accusatory	IT1.2
		Humility	IT1.3
	Consistency	Emotional control	IT2.4
		Accountability	IT2.5
		Comprehensive focus	IT2.6
	Courage	Courage	IT3.7
		Self-confidence	IT3.8

Table 3: Operational Variables of Teamwork (KS)

Variables	Dimension	Indicator	Code
Teamwork (KS)	Collaboration	Responsibility	KS1.1
		Helping Each Other	KS1.2
		Accepting Opinions	KS1.3
	Coordination	Unity of Action	KS2.4
		Division of Labor	KS2.5
	Communication	Understanding	KS3.6
		Action	KS3.7
	Comfort	Creating a Sense of Security	KS4.8
		Effective and Efficient Work Environment	KS4.9
	Problem Solving	Understanding Problems	KS5.10
		Problem-Solving Strategies	KS5.11
	Self-Confidence	Believing in One's Own Abilities	KS6.12
		Thinking Positively	KS6.13

Table 4: Operational Variables of Job Satisfaction (KP)

Variables	Dimension	Indicator	Code
Job Satisfaction (KP)	The Job Itself	Pride in Work	KP1.1
		Spirituality Inspiring Every Job	KP1.2
	Salary	Payment Appropriate to Workload	KP2.3
		Improved Living Needs	KP2.4
	Promotion Opportunities	Status/Career Enhancement	KP3.5
		Learning Opportunities	KP3.6
	Supervision	Employee Development Control	KP4.7
		Supervision While Working	KP4.8
	Coworkers	Personal Characteristics	KP5.9
		Sense of Shared Responsibility	KP5.10

Table 5: Operational Variables of Employee Performance (KN)

Variables	Dimension	Indicator	Code
Employee Performance (KN)	Quality of Work	Neatness	KN1.1
		Ability	KN1.2
		Success	KN1.3
	Quantity of Work	Speed	KN2.4
		Satisfaction	KN2.5
	Responsibility	Work Results	KN3.6
		Decision Making	KN3.7
		Facilities and Infrastructure	KN3.8
	Collaboration	Cohesiveness	KN4.9
		Good relationships with coworkers and superiors	KN4.10
	Initiative	Independence	KN5.11

RESEARCH RESULTS

Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 6: Score Range and Categories

Score	Score Interval	Category
1	1,00-1,80	Very Low/Very Poor
2	1,81-2,60	Low/Poor
3	2,61-3,40	Fairly High/Fairly Good
4	3,41-4,20	High/Good
5	4,21-5,00	Very High/Very Good

Source: Zikmund, William G., et. al (2010)

Table 7: Hybrid Measurement Model Fit – SEM

Goodness of Fit Indicators	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,81	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,036	Good Fit

Incremental Fit Size			
Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)	NNFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	NFI > 0,90	0,94	Good Fit
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	AGFI > 0,90	0,77	Marginal Fit
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	RFI > 0,90	0,93	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	IFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	CFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 8: Hybrid Model Measurement Analysis (Full Model)

Model Pengukuran		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t-Value
Latent Variable	Manifest Variable			
Transformational Leadership	Idealized Influence	0.83	0,069	10.91
	Inspirational Motivation	0.85	0,072	10.50
	Intellectual Stimulation	0.81	0,061	10.20
	Individualized Consideration	0.79	0,066	10.14
Integrity	Honesty	0.83	0,026	11.25
	Consistency	0.86	0,023	10.04
	Courage	0.84	0,031	10.26
Teamwork	Cooperation	0.82	0,033	10.67
	Coordination	0.82	0,029	10.06
	Communication	0.83	0,025	9.96
	Comfort	0.82	0,031	10.34
	Problem Solving	0.80	0,038	10.92
	Self-Confidence	0.85	0,023	10.83
Job Satisfaction	The Work Itself	0.83	0,031	6.39
	Salary	0.81	0,032	11.38
	Promotion Opportunities	0.83	0,031	11.40
	Supervision	0.83	0,030	11.40
	Coworkers	0.81	0,032	11.40
Employee Performance	Work Quality	0.81	0,019	11.26
	Quantity	0.82	0,018	9.80
	Responsibility	0.84	0,019	10.31
	Cooperation	0.84	0,018	10.34
	Initiative	0.80	0,020	9.95

Source: Processed data

Table 9: Summary of Test Results Between Latent Variables

No	Structural Path	Path Coefficient	t-value	t-table	Test Results
1	Transformational Leadership (KT) on Job Satisfaction (KP)	0,14	2,23	1,96	Significant
2	Integrity (IT) towards Job Satisfaction (KP)	0,17	4,33	1,96	Significant
3	Teamwork (KS) on Job Satisfaction (KP)	0,23	2,19	1,96	Significant
4	Transformational Leadership (KT) on Performance (KN)	0,14	2,61	1,96	Significant
5	Integrity (IT) towards Employee Performance (KN)	0,17	2,90	1,96	Significant
6	Teamwork (KS) on Employee Performance (KN)	0,26	2,44	1,96	Significant

7	Job Satisfaction (KP) towards Employee Performance (KN)	0,33	2,21	1,96	Significant
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Source: Processed data

Sub-Structural Equation 1

$$KP = 0.14*KT + 0.17*IT + 0.23*KS, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.30, R^2 = 0.70$$

$$\begin{matrix} (0.09) & (0.11) & (0.09) & (0.24) \\ 2.23 & 4.33 & 2.19 & 2.88 \end{matrix}$$

Sub-Structural Model 2 (t-Value)

$$KN = 0.33*KP + 0.14*KT + 0.17*IT + 0.26*KS, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.18, R^2 = 0.82$$

$$\begin{matrix} (0.14) & (0.07) & (0.0.7) & (0.07) & (0.07) \\ 2.21 & 2.61 & 2.90 & 2.44 & 2.55 \end{matrix}$$

Table 10: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Description	Path Coef.	tvalue/ Fvalue	tcriteria/ Fcriteria	Test Results
H1	$H_0 : \gamma_{11} = 0$	Transformational Leadership (KT) has no effect on Job Satisfaction (KP).	0,14	2,23	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Transformational Leadership (KT) has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction (KP).
	$H_a : \gamma_{11} \neq 0$	Transformational Leadership (KT) has an effect on Job Satisfaction (KP).				
H2	$H_0 : \gamma_{12} = 0$	Integrity (IT) has no effect on Job Satisfaction (KP).	0.17	4,33	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Integrity (I) has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction (KP).
	$H_a : \gamma_{12} \neq 0$	Integrity (IT) has an effect on Job Satisfaction (KP).				
H3	$H_0 : \gamma_{13} = 0$	Teamwork (KS) has no effect on Job Satisfaction (KP)	0.23	2,19	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Teamwork (KS) has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction (KP).
	$H_a : \gamma_{13} \neq 0$	Teamwork (KS) has an effect on Job Satisfaction (KP)				
H4	$H_0 : \gamma_{21} = 0$	Transformational Leadership (KT) has no effect on Employee Performance (KN)	0,14	2,61	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Transformational Leadership (KT) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (KN).
	$H_a : \gamma_{21} \neq 0$	Transformational Leadership (KT) has an effect on Employee Performance (KN)				
H5	$H_0 : \gamma_{22} = 0$	Integrity (IT) has no effect on Employee Performance (KN)	0,17	2,90	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Integrity (I) has a positive and significant effect on
	$H_a : \gamma_{22} \neq 0$	Integrity (IT) has an effect on Employee Performance (KN)				

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Description	Path Coef.	tvalue/ Fvalue	tcriteria/ Fcriteria	Test Results
						Employee Performance (KN).
H6	$H_0: \gamma_{23} = 0$	Teamwork (KS) has no effect on Employee Performance (KN)	0,26	2,44	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Teamwork (KS) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (KN).
	$H_a: \gamma_{23} \neq 0$	Teamwork (KS) has an effect on Employee Performance (KN)				
H7	$H_0: \beta_{21} = 0$	Job Satisfaction (KP) has no effect on Employee Performance (KN)	0,33	2,21	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Job Satisfaction (KP) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (KN).
	$H_a: \beta_{21} \neq 0$	Job Satisfaction (KP) has an effect on Employee Performance (KN).				

Source: Processed data

H₁: Transformational Leadership has a significant influence and positive correlation with Job Satisfaction.

H₂: Integrity is positively correlated and has a significant influence on Job Satisfaction.

H₃: Teamwork has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a positive correlation..

H₄: Transformational Leadership has a significant influence with a positive correlation on Employee Performance.

H₅: Integrity has a significant positive correlation with Employee Performance.

H₆: Teamwork is positively correlated and has a significant influence on Employee Performance.

H₇: Job Satisfaction has a significant positive correlation with Employee Performance.

CONCLUSION

Job Satisfaction is the dominant variable on the Employee Performance variable for employees of Manufacturing Companies in the West Cikarang Industrial Area, West Java, where the Job Satisfaction variable can successfully mediate and explain its influence on the research problem, namely Employee Performance.

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